

An Economic Theory of Special Censuses and Population Estimates Challenges

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Abstract

Population estimates and decennial census populations are used as the basis for funding from the Federal government to the States and from the States to their localities. These funds are often allocated on a per capita basis. Depending on the law, either the latest decennial or estimated population is used for funding. Likewise, it is often possible for a locality to either conduct a special census or to challenge its estimate. This paper models these processes by assuming that each locality possesses a rational agent who has perfect information about the structure of the model and acts to maximize the locality's income. The actor's cost-benefit analysis is modeled. Challenges are assumed to be costless and lead to a ceteris paribus prediction that the locality's population does not affect its probability of a challenge. Special censuses are costly and lead to a ceteris paribus prediction that the probability of a special census increases with the population size. Implications of these results for population estimates are explored. Statistical tests find that the probabilities of special censuses and challenges both increase in population size.

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1. Introduction

Population estimates and decennial census populations are used as the basis for funding from the Federal government to the States and from the States to their localities. These funds are allocated on a per capita basis. Depending on the law, either the latest census count or estimated population is used for funding. Likewise, it is often possible for a locality to either conduct a special census at its expense or to challenge its estimate. A special census is a census taken specifically at the locality's request at a time not prespecified by law (such as the decennial U.S. census.) A challenge is an attempt to change the U.S. Census Bureau's official population estimate for a specific postcensal year. Each locality is assumed to possess a rational, risk-neutral¹ agent who acts to maximize the locality's income using his perfect information about the model described in this paper. Maximizing income is not the only reason for special censuses and population estimates challenges: localities may wish to have accurate counts for planning and provision of services.² Other pecuniary motivations for special censuses and estimates challenges are not considered. These include attaining population thresholds to obtain program funds and depressing populations to obtain other program funds. It is also assumed that decennial census counts and postcensal population estimates have no systematic bias as a function of locality size.

The idea of using population to apportion representation in the House of Representatives and direct taxation comes from the U.S. Constitution, Article I, Section 2, Clause 3:

“Representatives and direct Taxes shall be apportioned among the several States which may be included within this Union, according to their respective Numbers, which shall be determined by adding to the whole Number of free Persons, including those bound to Service for a Term of Years, and excluding Indians not taxed, three fifths of all other Persons. The actual Enumeration shall be made within three Years after the first Meeting of the Congress of the United States, and within every subsequent Term of ten Years, in such Manner as they shall by Law direct.”

This text provides for the taking of a decennial census for the aforementioned purposes. Apportionment of revenues

¹Risk neutrality is not necessary. Risk aversion can be accommodated by increasing the cost of a special census, with no difference in the conclusions. Likewise, in the case of challenges, it has little substantial effect.

²However, it should be noted that these purposes may be subject to public choice considerations.

according to population is a direct extension, first done in 1836, when a Federal surplus of over \$36,000,000 was distributed to the states in proportion to their 1830 enumerated populations. This set a precedent for future Federal spending. In 1979, the Federal government allocated approximately \$100 in revenues to every resident by way of transfers to the states and localities. (Keyfitz, 1979, p. 45) Since decennial census data are obsolete once the census has been made, with the divergence between the enumerated and actual populations growing over time, population estimates have become increasingly important.³ The U.S. Census Bureau first produced subnational estimates in 1902. Today, they are regularly produced for states, metropolitan areas, counties and subcounty areas.⁴ These estimates have been used for Federal revenue-sharing.⁵ Similar to the growth of Federal transfers to the states, transfers from states to localities have grown significantly. These transfers originated in the shared tax, in which the state government collects taxes on behalf of individual localities and returns the proceeds. Since their inception, shared taxes have been gradually replaced by direct grants from states to localities. (Maxwell and Aronson, 1977, Chapter 4) These grants are often made in proportion to decennial census or postcensal estimated populations.

A special census or population estimate challenge is assumed to be made when it maximizes the expected value of a locality's population after the challenge or special census. A locality is taken to be any subnational geographic area with a general-purpose government.⁶ Section 2 builds a unified model of these processes. One result common to both cases is that the populations of localities which do not challenge or undertake special censuses are systematically overestimated. Challenges are assumed costless and are more fully explored in Subsection 2.1. Special censuses are

³This finesses the problem of census miscount. It is quite possible that estimated postcensal population shares will converge to the enumerated shares in the presence of census miscount. However, this is unlikely, as it requires the assumption that population flows from overcounted areas to undercounted ones. Economic theory posits the exact opposite: undercounted areas tend to have below average wages, so their residents will leave for other, higher-wage areas, in the absence of constraints on their movements.

⁴Subcounty areas include incorporated villages, towns and cities; minor civil divisions, also known as towns or townships (these form complete, mutually exclusive partitions of counties in New England and several Midwestern states); and the unincorporated balances of counties and minor civil divisions.

⁵Spencer (1986, pp. 397-398) claims that the then-used Federal general revenue sharing formula, in spite of its complexity, was almost equivalent to allocation by population alone. The complexity resulted from political considerations, which themselves are worthy of investigation.

⁶In addition to states and counties, these include the subcounty areas note in footnote 4, with the exception of unincorporated balances, as these, by definition, have no general-purpose government specifically associated with them.

costly and are considered in Subsection 2.2. These Subsections find that the model predicts that population has no effect on the probability of a challenge, while it positively increases the probability of a special census. Section 3 statistically tests these hypotheses. Subsection 3.1 uses data from Utah challenges to the 1998 population estimates from the Census Bureau's Population Estimates Branch's 1999 version of subcounty estimates. Subsection 3.2 uses Arkansas special censuses conducted since the 1990 decennial census. In both cases, population positively affects the probability of a challenge or special census. These results have to be interpreted with caution because of possible confounding, missing variables and misspecification. In all regressions, R^2 is less than 0.1, indicating that very little of the variation is explained. Section 4 concludes this paper.

2. The Model

The locality chooses to challenge its estimate or conduct a special census if the expected value of the resulting revenue stream exceeds the expected cost of conducting the challenge or census.⁷ It is assumed that only one period's funding is affected by this decision. If multiple periods are affected, the conclusions are strengthened. The expected benefit of the special census or challenge to locality i is

$$\pi(\mathbf{E}P'_i - P_i) \tag{1}$$

where π is the (fixed) per capita revenue,⁸ and P_i and P'_i are the populations before and after the census or challenge, respectively. The cost of conducting the census or challenge consists of a fixed cost a and a per capita (marginal) cost b , both of which are nonnegative:

$$a + b\mathbf{E}P'_i . \tag{2}$$

Locality i chooses to challenge or take a census whenever expression (1) exceeds expression (2):

$$\pi(\mathbf{E}P'_i - P_i) > a + b\mathbf{E}P'_i . \tag{3}$$

⁷All of the expectations herein are taken with respect to a subjective probability distribution per Savage (1954).

⁸Using the proportion of total revenues allocated, the alternative to using fixed per capita revenue, would unnecessarily complicate the model while providing no additional insights.

This can be solved for $\mathbf{E}P'_i$:

$$\mathbf{E}P'_i > \frac{a + \pi P_i}{\pi - b} . \quad (4)$$

Equation (4) has a simple intuitive interpretation. The numerator is the fixed cost of the special census plus the current total revenue. This sum is the shadow fixed cost of the census or challenge: the fixed cost of the census or challenge itself plus the current revenue foregone. The denominator is the net per capita benefit of the census or challenge. Clearly, $\pi > b$.⁹ Otherwise, the expected benefit would be negative and it would not be rational to undertake the census or challenge. The right-hand side is the ratio of the shadow cost to the per capita benefit. This is the population required to break even on the special census or challenge. If the expected population after the census or challenge is greater, then the census or challenge is undertaken.

In the work below, it is assumed that censuses are costly: both $a, b > 0$. Challenges are costless: $a = b = 0$. The rationale for the latter assumption is that challenges are done administratively. The actor is assumed to be on his locality's payroll for other purposes and performs the challenge in the course of his duties. He is assumed to have costless access to the data with which he makes the challenge. For example, he may collect the data for other purposes in the normal course of his duties. Making the challenge itself requires minimal time and resources.

2.1 Challenges

In the case of a challenge, equation (4) reduces to

$$\mathbf{E}P'_i > P_i . \quad (5)$$

This has the obvious interpretation: a challenge is made whenever the locality believes it has (or, at least, can make a case for) a higher population than its estimate. The challenge decision is independent of the locality's size; therefore,

⁹If revenue for k periods is affected, then $k\pi > b$, assuming a zero discount rate. (If the discount rate is positive then k in the previous inequality is replaced by a smaller constant, reflecting the net present value of the future revenues.) Thus, in a multiperiod setting, it can be rational to undertake a census or challenge and incur a one-time cost (i.e., $k\pi > b$ and $\pi < b$).

ceteris paribus,¹⁰ the size of a locality has no effect on its probability of challenging. Another implication follows immediately: localities which do not challenge are systematically overestimated; otherwise, they would challenge.

The challenge itself consists of proposing a population $P_i'' > P_i$, with a subjective probability of acceptance p , $0 < p < 1$.¹¹ Thus,

$$EP_i' = pP_i'' + (1-p)P_i. \quad (6)$$

It is reasonable to assume that p is a function of P_i'' . That is, the probability of the challenge's acceptance is a function of the proposed population. Clearly, if $P_i'' = P_i$, $p = 1$. p is then assumed to be continuous and to decline monotonically in P_i'' until it reaches zero: $dp/dP_i'' < 0$. That p eventually reaches 0 at a finite value of P_i'' can be seen by picking an enormous P_i'' , say, twice the world's population. This challenge is clearly unreasonable: thus, for it, $p = 0$.

Substituting $p(P_i'')$ for p in equation (6) and taking the derivative with respect to P_i'' obtains the equation of optimality for a challenge:

$$p(P_i'') + (P_i'' - P_i) \frac{dp(P_i'')}{dP_i''} = 0. \quad (7)$$

Without knowing the form of $p(P_i'')$, it is impossible to solve (7). However, equation (7) does show the trade-off involved. We begin by observing that, when $P_i'' = P_i$, the left-hand side of equation (7) is unity, while for $P_i'' \gg P_i$, the same side is negative since $p(P_i'') = 0$ and the term on the right side of the addition is negative. Therefore, the

¹⁰This is Latin for "all other things being equal." That is, all factors which have not been explicitly accounted for are ruled out.

¹¹It is not necessary for the original population to be inaccurate, as long the actor has a positive subjective probability of acceptance. This abstracts from reputational effects in repeated contexts.

equation will be in balance for at least one value of P_i'' . It is reasonable to assume that the largest such value is

proposed. A sufficient condition for uniqueness is $\frac{d^2 p(P_i'')}{(dP_i'')^2} < 2(P_i - P_i'') \frac{dp(P_i'')}{dP_i''}$ for all P_i'' .¹² Linear $p(P_i'')$ clearly

satisfies this condition.

2.1.1 Implications for County Estimates Methodology

The Census Bureau has used several methods for estimating county populations. These fall into two main categories: top-down and bottom-up. The top-down method first estimates state total populations and then allocates these populations to the component counties. The bottom-up method produces estimates for counties only, then sums these to obtain state totals. If both methods are subject to challenges, then the bottom-up method is preferable. If a state challenges its total in a top-down method, any change in the total is distributed to all counties. This distribution does not take into account county-level variations in population changes. Moreover, the burden of proof of challenge is lower than in a bottom-up method. In a bottom-up method, a challenge can only be made to a particular county. If a state were to make the challenge itself, it would have to state exactly which counties were underestimated.

2.2 Special Censuses

As stated before, special censuses are costly. The simplest way to study these is to look at them at the limits of the P_i . For the purposes of this analysis, these limits are taken to be one and infinity. When $P_i = 1$, equation (4) becomes

$$EP_i' > \frac{\alpha + \pi}{\pi - b} > 1. \tag{8}$$

The rightmost inequality is not surprising: it just reiterates the fact that a special census is desirable whenever the

¹²This inequality can be obtained by noting that the derivative of equation (7) at the optimum is nonpositive. Making it negative produces a unique solution. The resulting inequality is then rearranged to obtain the uniqueness condition.

expected value of the new population exceeds the current population. However, the middle term is likely to be far more than 1. Any value of a significantly greater than π will lead to a special census's not being undertaken. For example, if $a = 10,000$, $b = 0$ and $\pi = 100$, then that term becomes 101, which is two orders of magnitude greater than 1. Only in rare cases of gross initial underenumeration will this be the case. At the other extreme, as P_i diverges, inequality (4) converges to

$$\mathbf{E}P'_i > P_i. \quad (9)$$

Thus, a large area undertakes a special census whenever the expected new population is greater than the current population. Taken together, these results indicate that the probability of a special census increases in the population of an area. Similar to the case of challenges, the probability that the population of a non-special census locality is overestimated increases in its population.

The points of the preceding paragraph can be made clearer by assuming that each locality receives money in proportion to its regular census population, unless a special census is taken. Further, assume that each locality has grown uniformly, so that $P'_i = gP_i$ for all i . To understand this case, we begin by reexpressing inequality (4):

$$\mathbf{E}P'_i = gP_i > \frac{a + \pi P_i}{\pi - b}. \quad (10)$$

Solving inequality (10) for g obtains

$$g > \frac{a + \pi P_i}{(\pi - b)P_i} = \frac{a}{(\pi - b)P_i} + \frac{\pi}{\pi - b}. \quad (11)$$

As g rises, the special census threshold P_i falls. Equivalently, as P_i rises, the threshold growth rate g falls. The implication is still the same: larger localities are more likely to have special censuses than smaller ones.

3. Statistical Results

This Section tests the hypotheses developed in the previous Section, namely, that the probability of a challenge is not affected by the reported population and that the probability of a special census increases in the reported population. It

should be noted that, due to confounding by missing variables, these tests are exploratory in nature and should not be taken to be definitive. In both cases, summary statistics are first displayed. Because the data are not expected to be independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.), ANOVA tests and their variants cannot be used. Instead, the probability of a challenge or special census is estimated by three methods. Two methods, ordinary least squares (OLS) and least absolute deviations (LAD), estimate the linear model: $\text{PROBABILITY} = a + b * \text{POPULATION}$.¹³ The advantage of using a robust estimator like LAD is that it can account for the nonnormality of the errors caused by missing variables. (Levy 2000) It may also be robust against misspecification. In every case, the dependent variable is 1 if a challenge or special census occurs and 0 otherwise. It is therefore a limited dependent variable, for which the probit is appropriate. The probit estimates the probability of a challenge or special census as $\Phi(a + b * \text{POPULATION})$, where Φ is the standard normal cumulative distribution. A caution about the probit is in order: it is a maximum-likelihood estimator based on i.i.d. normal errors. There is little reason to believe this to be the case. Unfortunately, to this author's knowledge, there are no robust variants of the probit.

Both data sets consist of all incorporated places¹⁴ in a particular state, except those places which had special censuses as part of a county special census. Each state was chosen for the frequency of challenges or special censuses. Utah had 10 challenges out of a total of 219 places, or 4.6%. Arkansas had 31 special censuses in the 461 places which did not have county-wide special censuses. In all cases, the geography is that used for the 1998 round of Census Bureau subcounty population estimates and was current as of 1997. In cases of annexations or deannexations since 1990, the geography does not correspond to the 1990 census. In some cases, it is possible that boundary changes made between 1990 and 1997 were not picked up by the Census Bureau.

3.1 Challenges

¹³Linear probability specifications have been used for binary dependent variables. See, for example, Denk and Finkel (1992). The linear model seems particularly appropriate if one assumes that the effect on PROBABILITY of a change in POPULATION is independent of the initial value of PROBABILITY. (Denk and Finkel, 1992:788)

¹⁴In the Census Bureau's terminology, these are known as 'State Places' with summary level '162'.

The dataset consists of the 1998 Census Bureau population estimates of incorporated places in Utah, per the June 30, 1999 Census Bureau release. Table 1 shows summary statistics for all, challenging and nonchallenging places.

Table 1
Summary Statistics for Utah Places' 1998 Estimated Populations

	Observation Set		
	All	Challenging Places	Nonchallenging Places
number	229	10	219
mean	7461	30985	6387
median	1416	5452	1307
standard deviation	19358	37726	17510
minimum	34	96	34
maximum	174350	99372	174350

Note: All statistics are shown with zero decimals.

Table 1 shows that, contrary to the hypothesis of Subsection 2.1, challenging places tend to be larger than nonchallengers: their population means, medians and minima are larger. Table 2 displays the regression results for the three estimators.

Table 2
Utah Regression Results

	Technique		
	OLS	LAD	Probit
Intercept	.023126 (1.65)*	.022493 (1.61)	-1.8997 (11.04)**
1998 Population	2.7533E-4 (4.06)**	2.7335E-4 (4.04)**	1.3905E-3 (2.99)**
R^2	.068	.068	.039
R^2 adj.	.064	-	-
Number of Cases Correctly Predicted			218

t-ratios in parentheses

* Significant at 10%, two-tailed test

** Significant at 1%, two-tailed test

Table 2 shows that all methods have highly significant positive coefficients for the 1998 Population, contrary to the zero prediction of Subsection 2.1.¹⁵ As noted above, this does not necessarily refute the hypothesis, due to missing variables. For example, organizational ability or awareness of the importance, or even the existence, of the estimates may be increasing in population size.¹⁶ These can produce the result seen herein, while the maintained hypothesis remains true. The results of the two linear methods are practically indistinguishable, indicating little gain to using robust regression. Finally, they appear to have greater explanatory power. Their R^2 s are larger, while the probit correctly predicted only one challenge.

3.2 Special Censuses

The dataset for testing the special census hypothesis is all incorporated places in counties in Arkansas except places in

¹⁵Note that $\Phi(-1.8997) = .028736$, which is close to the intercepts estimated by the linear specifications. This indicates broad agreement between the probit and the linear models: the estimated probability of a challenge when the 1998 population is zero varies little between the specifications.

¹⁶All of these explanations represent departures from the perfect information assumption.

Baxter, Craighead and Washington Counties, which had county-wide censuses. This state was chosen for its relative abundance of special censuses: 31 of 461, or 6.7%, places in the remaining counties. The special census data were obtained from the Institute for Economic Advancement, College of Business Administration, University of Arkansas at Little Rock. The independent variable is the total population from the 1990 Census. Table 3 displays summary statistics for these places and for places with fewer than 30,000 residents in 1990. The reason for omitting places of over 30,000 from the second set of observations has to do with the omission of Fayetteville and Jonesboro from the analysis: both of these places had 1990 populations of over 40,000. Since these places did not have the opportunity to seek special censuses on their own, their omissions could bias the 1990 Population coefficient downwards.

Table 3

Summary Statistics for Arkansas Places' 1990 Census Populations

	Observation Set					
	All Places			Places with 1990 Population Less than 30,000		
	All	Places with Special Censuses	Places without Special Censuses	All	Places with Special Censuses	Places without Special Censuses
number	461	31	430	456	31	425
mean	2820	6392	2562	1972	6392	1650
median	521	2239	489	513	2239	488
standard deviation	10444	7733	10573	4114	7733	3523
minimum	38	169	38	38	169	38
maximum	175727	26481	175727	29101	26481	29101

Note: All statistics are shown with zero decimals.

Table 3 clearly shows that places with special censuses tend to be more populous than places without. In both sets, the mean, median and minimum 1990 population of places with special censuses is larger than those without.

Table 4 reports the regression results for the Arkansas data. They are very similar to the Utah results, in that population always has a significant, positive coefficient, albeit at frequently higher significance levels. Again, the linear

specification outperforms the probit, for similar reasons. The most striking differences are between the two datasets. Excluding places of over 30,000 population resulted in increases in R^2 : from .009 to .084 in the linear cases and a more dramatic rise from .002 to .069 in the probit. In comparison to its other uses in this paper, this probit looks plausible. In all models, the intercepts' t -ratios fall, while those of the 1990 population rise.

Table 4
Arkansas Regression Results

Observation Set	All Places			Places with 1990 Population less than 30,000		
	Technique			Technique		
	OLS	LAD	Probit	OLS	LAD	Probit
Intercept	.06021 (5.06)***	.060239 (5.00)***	-1.54 (16.38)***	.032893 (2.62)***	.032232 (2.57)***	-1.7259 (15.78)***
1990 Population	2.2071E-6 (1.98)**	2.188E-6 (1.96)**	1.0713E-5 (1.82)*	1.17791E-5 (6.47)***	1.7754E-5 (6.46)***	7.5976E-5 (4.86)***
R^2	.009	.009	.002	.084	.084	.069
R^2 adj.	.006	-	-	.082	-	-
Number of Cases Correctly Predicted			429			424

t -ratios in parentheses

- * Significant at 10%, two-tailed test
- ** Significant at 5%, two-tailed test
- *** Significant at 1%, two-tailed test

4. Conclusion

This paper has built a unified theory of special censuses and population estimates challenges by assuming that each locality is apportioned revenues from a higher-level government in proportion to its population. Furthermore, each locality employs a rational actor who has perfect information about the process embedded in the model. Excluding other pecuniary effects from population changes, the model predicts that population does not affect the probability of a challenge, while it increases the probability of a special census. Since localities which were already accurately counted

or overcounted have no incentive to increase their populations, they do not challenge or pay for a special census. Thus, they are systematically overestimated. Another implication arises for population estimates methodology: bottom-up estimates are preferable to top-down ones, when both are challengeable. That is, it is better estimate counties and aggregate them to states than to estimate states and disaggregate them to counties. Finally, inspection of population averages, medians and minima and a variety of regression techniques find that the probability of a challenge or special census increases in the population. The results are weak statistically and may be subject to confounding, missing variables and misspecification. Thus, they should be regarded with caution. Future research may be able to refine the statistics by identifying and quantifying institutional factors and by incorporating threshold effects, to give but two examples.

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